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TRANSLATION PROBLEMS OF RELIGIOUS PROPER NOUNS

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Annotation: *This article analyzes similarities and differences between the religious proper nouns in holy religious books taken from Uzbek and English languages. It also expresses some ways of translating religious proper nouns to solve the linguistic problems during translation.*

Key words: *proper nouns, religious books, names of places, prophets, translation theory.*

DINIY ATOQLI OTLARNI TARJIMA QILISH MUAMMOLARI

Ziyodjon Sharipov

Qo'qon shahri

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi diniy kitoblarda keltirilgan atoqli otlarning o'xshash va farqli jihatlari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, maqolada diniy ma'noga ega atoqli otlarni tarjima qilish jarayonida yuzaga keladigan ba'zi muammolarga yechimlar haqida so'z boradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *atoqli otlar, diniy kitoblar, joy nomlari, payg'ambarlar, tarjima nazariyasi.*

The study of proper principle of translation is termed as translation theory. Catford: translation is the replacement of textual material in one language by equivalent textual material in another language emphasizes the concept of equivalence and meaning in two or more languages. This theory, based on a solid foundation on understanding of how languages work, translation theory recognizes that different languages encode meaning in differing forms, yet guides translators to find appropriate ways of preserving meaning, while using the most appropriate forms of each language. Translation theory includes principles for translating figurative language, dealing with lexical mismatches, rhetorical questions, inclusion of cohesion markers, and many other topics crucial to good translation. Basically there are two competing theories of translation. In one, the predominant purpose is to express as exactly as possible the full force and meaning of every word and turn of phrase in the original, and in the other the predominant purpose is to produce a result that does not read like a translation at all, but rather moves in its new dress with the same ease as in its native rendering.

In the hands of a good translator neither of these two approaches can ever be entirely ignored. Conventionally, it is suggested that in order to perform their job successfully, translators should meet three important requirements; they should be familiar with:

- the source language
- the target language
- the subject matter⁴

Based on this premise, the translator discovers the meaning behind the forms in the source language and does his best to produce the same meaning in the target language - using the forms and structures of the target language. Consequently, what is supposed to change is the form and the code and what should remain unchanged is the meaning and the message. Crystal called the science that studies names as onomastics (Greek onomastikos from onoma 'name'), which is usually divided into the study of personal names (anthroponomastics from Greek anthropos 'human being') and place names (toponomastics from Greek topos 'place'). As he stated, the term onomastics is used to refer to personal names and toponomastics to place names. He considered this division an arbitrary one, as places can be named after people (e.g. Alberta in Canada is named after the fourth daughter of Queen Victoria, Princess Louise Caroline Alberta) and vice versa: Israel is also used as a first name). Matthews stated that the special nature of names is often described in terms of the differences between proper nouns and common nouns. Proper noun is interpreted here as "the name of a specific individual or of a set of individuals distinguished only by their having that name.

Strawson believed that, unlike generic nouns, proper names are mono-referential. Their main function is to identify an individual referent. He has claimed that proper names lack descriptive meaning: An ordinary personal name is, roughly, a word, used to refer to sth/sb, the use of which is not dictated by any descriptive meaning the word may have. The Finnish scholar in Onomastics Eero Kiviniemi and Hanks and Hodges introduced anthroponymy as an established and approved system of personal names in every language, which the speakers of that language easily recognize as conventional names belonging to the system of ordinary names. According to them proper names are, to some degree, culturally and linguistically specific although some names and name forms are universal, which means that one and the same name is used in more than one language. For example first names originating from biblical persons (Christian names) and saints are the most widespread; other historical persons have been influential too.

In the light of the theoretical information and practical analysis of translating Arabic proper nouns into English. The following points can be drawn:

⁴Juan Daniel Pérez Vallejo Translation teacher, University of Cd. Del Carmen, Campeche, Mexico

1. Accurate translation should fulfill the same purpose in the target language as the original did in the source language, a condition which can hardly be achieved in translating religious texts in general and proper nouns in particular. This is, in fact, the main reason for losing much in the process of translation.

2. Some translators adopt explaining or paraphrasing the Arabic proper nouns for there are no equivalent synonyms in English. This is not a shortage in translation as it is language-specific characteristics.

3. Differences among translators in translating Arabic proper nouns are due to their reliance on certain Quranic interpreters. Indeed, translating such texts demands consulting specialized scholars, for many texts imply rules, instructions, orders, etc.

4. Most translators prefer the cultural transplantation in translating Arabic proper nouns (those figure names mentioned in Quran). With the Arabic modern nouns the transliteration method is preferable.

5. Some translators use footnote to give more detail and explanation to the Arabic vague proper nouns (to the foreigners), for the linguistic and cultural factors have great role in clarifying the intended meaning. Most religious proper nouns taken from the Holy books like Koran and Bible go back to the same phonetic root because of their Arabic origin despite the fact that they are pronounced and interpreted differently through their phonetic system. Scholars believe that many proper nouns in Koran and Bible denotes the same person as their transcription and spelling features are much more similar. Here are some versions of religious proper names which denotes the same person or place taken from holy religious books:

Uzbek version	English version
Ibrohim	Abraham
Mikoyil	Michael
Jabroil	Gabriel
Israfil	Rafael
Shayton	Satan or devil
Yaqub	Jacob
Odam a.s.	Adam
Suleyman	Solomon
Yunus	Jonah
Yusuf	Joseph
Nuh	Noah
Fir'avn	Pharaoh

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Yahudiy	Hebrew	
Dovud	David	
Suleyman	Solomon	
Maryam	Mary	
Is'hoq	Isaac	

To conclude, results of translating personal nouns revealed that there is no unified recipe for translating religious proper nouns, especially, names of people. Various procedures might be used in translating such personal names whether they were used singly or collaboratively. Some ways are suggested in this article but with different proportions for each. However, couplets with different variations seemed to be the most common procedure used by the participants. Then, the recognized translation or the equivalent was hugely used as well as transliteration. Functional translation, word-for-word and transposition were also used but with very little proportions. Translators did not always use the same technique in translating religious proper nouns rather they use more than one technique.

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